

THE EDEN AVENUE CASE: A SMALL DOMESTIC EXTENSION PROJECT

Project background:

The Eden Avenue project was a small two-bedroom house in the middle of a row housing in Riley for Mr Joe Antonio. The residence had a very small kitchen and an associated living area, two bedrooms and a bathroom on the upper floor. The intention of the Client was to extend the ground level so as to increase the kitchen size and to give better dining and lounge areas on the ground floor with access to a rear garden. The rear garden of the Eden Avenue residence with the extension work is indicated in Exhibit 1.

Exhibit 1: Extension work at a rear garden of Eden Avenue residence.

The cost of the extension work was £30,000 and took six months to complete – March, 2018 to August, 2018. Originally, the Client knew a local builder that he had considered to undertake the project and thus wanted a design to proceed with the development. He therefore approached a local Architect for assistance with the design. The Architect advised the Client to adopt the JCT Minor Works Building Contract for the works to protect himself as well as the builder in the event of payment challenges. The Client, initially, was not comfortable with the advice regarding the use of a formal contract as he felt such a small work did not merit an arrangement in that form. Similarly, the local builder (who operated in an informal market and often referred to as a ‘cowboy builder’) initially declined the idea of a formal contract.

Exhibit 2: Existing plans of Eden Avenue residence

Exhibit 3: Proposed ground floor plan of Eden Avenue residence showing the extension

However, eventually, upon the insistence of the Architect, a traditional procurement method, using a JCT Minor Works Building Contract, was deployed in carrying out the project.

There was no formal briefing document from the Client to the Project Architect, except to inform the Architect that he needed an extension to his house. The lack of a specific indication of the Client's preference via a formal brief from the outset led to an evolving project brief during the project development. See Exhibits 2 and 3 for the existing and proposed plans, respectively.

Client's General H&S Arrangements

The Client was not aware of Construction (Design and Management) Regulations 2015 (CDM 2015) issues prior to the project and failed to make formal appointments to the Principal Designer (PD) and the Principal Contractor (PC) roles. This account confirms the already-held view that there is lack of or inadequate H&S knowledge among domestic clients in the construction industry. Notwithstanding, since the project was a minor domestic work, the CDM 2015 automatically required the designer in charge of the pre-construction phase and the contractor in charge of the construction phase to coordinate health and safety (H&S) matters, accordingly, at those phases of the project development process. Thus, the Project Architect assumed that role from the design stage to project completion and provided support to the Client regarding CDM responsibilities.

Additionally, the Project Architect assisted the Client to obtain a certificate of non-requirement of planning approval as the work was deemed to be within a permitted development right. Following the receipt of the certificate of non-requirement of planning approval, the Project Architect supported the Client to assemble other project parties to the project. For instance, the Client invited three local builders to tender for the work, including the Client's originally targeted local builder. To ascertain the competences of the three local builders, the Project Architect advised the Client to check some of the previous works of each of the builders and specifically talk to some of the neighbours who had engaged them in the past. Upon the checks on the previous works of the builders, it was found out that the performances of the builders were comparable so the Client selected the lowest tenderer. Unfortunately, the originally targeted local builder was not selected on the basis of price.

The selected builder through its own arrangements engaged the services of a local building surveyor to produce the building regulation drawings. Prior to the engagement of the local building surveyor by the builder, the Client upon the advice of the Project Architect requested to satisfy itself with the H&S competence of the prospective building surveyor. Agreement was, thus, reached between the Client and the builder to engage a building surveyor with chartered membership of Royal Institution of Chartered Surveyors (RICS). H&S competency evidence from frameworks such as Safety Schemes in Procurement (SSIP) was not considered proportionate and was not advised by the Project Architect to the Client regarding the competency assessment of the project dutyholders. Further, through the arrangements of the builder, a Structural Engineer, with chartered membership of The Institution of Structural Engineers, was brought on board to assist with all structural-related issues. The assistance offered by the PD to the Client in respect of getting the right people to the project highlights a

pervasive practice in the industry (i.e. bespoke use of repeat appointment of dutyholders already assessed for skills, knowledge, experience (SKE)) regarding assembling the project supply chain with focus on H&S. Additionally, the PD's role in ensuring that other project participants are competent, particularly from a H&S perspective, is not a duty of the PD but often carried out as Client expectation. This unearths an extra vital but non-regulatory PD function in the industry.

The H&S arrangements were considered proportionate to the scale of the project. The Project Architect specified a roof light in the building extension for maximum sunlight. As a result, before start on site, he had a meeting with the builder in the presence of the Client to discuss how to access and construct the roof safely. He particularly pointed out the fragility of the glass for the roof light and cautioned the builder to develop a safe method to install it. Exhibit 4 indicates a section of the building extension with the roof light.

Exhibit 4: A section of the extension area with roof light

The Project Architect assisted the builder to put together a simple Construction Phase Plan (CPP) before commencement of work on site. Further, the new extension was to go over a common sewer running through the rear gardens of the row housing. Hence, the PD in one of

the pre-construction project meeting proposed a concrete beam around it for maximum safety and protection. See Exhibit 5 for the proposed section with the concrete beam around the sewer.

Exhibit 5: Proposed section with a concrete beam around the sewer

There were challenges with access to the site from the front of the building via a car park with children playing around. Due to this restriction, the PD recommended that the rear garden served as an access point for building materials. These access challenges were pointed to the builder at the pre-construction stage of the project development process by the PD.

At the pre-construction stage of the project development process, the PD spent averagely five hours per month on the project to coordinate H&S related-related matters. After the appointment of the builder, a lot of the arrangements prior to appropriate start on site (i.e. production of building regulation drawings, structural analysis of the existing building, among others) were taken over by the builder with the supervision of the PD.

This project saw an active involvement of the PD regarding the Client's general H&S arrangements. However, that was so because the CDM automatically offloads such responsibilities on the professionals the Client engages, particularly in the case of domestic works and Clients. In practice, this phenomenon is not different from non-domestic Clients who are under duty to make suitable arrangements on projects to secure H&S. Such Clients when faced with the need to comply with the Regulation of making suitable H&S arrangements often resort to an approach such as dependence on third party health and safety arrangements. For example, Principal Designers (PDs), CDM advisors, and health and safety consultants, an approach often adopted by small and medium-scale non-domestic Clients who do not possess sufficient H&S capabilities in-house.

Organisation:

There was no specific organogram for the management of H&S on the project. The Project Architect, who doubled as the PD, was responsible for the coordination of H&S issues during the pre-construction stage of the project. The local building surveyor worked under the PD and did not take on H&S duties. The surveyor had a good relationship with the building control officers and also had worked with the builder in the past. Communication among the dutyholders, on the project, was generally considered good due to prior relationships and engagements. The responsibility for the management of H&S was deemed single-lined. The local building surveyor and the Structural Engineer although were brought on the project through the builder's arrangements worked cordially under the PD who assisted the Client with H&S responsibilities. The organisational structure for the delivery of H&S on the project and a simple project responsibility matrix are indicated in Exhibits 6 and 7, respectively.

Principal CDM Documents Preparation:

The preparation of the pre-construction information (PCI) started from the time the Project Architect (i.e. PD) was invited to the site by the Client to conduct site analysis. Sketches of the existing building and the proposed extensions were done by the Project Architect and agreed with by the Client after the site analysis visit. Subsequently, detailed drawing were produced. Further, the PCI included sign-posting H&S-related information in a JCT Minor Building Works contract, adjacent issues and assess restrictions to the site. It also included an agreement by the adjoining properties or neighbours which was a planning application requirement. There was no existing H&S File (HSF) on the building. The Project Architect had earlier done a simple survey on the building to indicate where the electrical systems and wire were located. Also, it was found out through the survey conducted by the Project Architect that there was no asbestos present in the building. There was also no gas in the building. All these information (i.e. PCI) were communicated to the builder via the detailed drawings submitted by the Project Architect.

The health and safety file (HSF) was basically the drawings that were produced by the local building surveyor. Attention was paid to the location of the new sewer arrangement underneath the building extension in the drawings. Exhibits 8a – 8c indicate the elevations of the Eden Avenue residential extension works; location of new sewer arrangement marked on the drawings of the extension area by the PD; and excerpts of notes of H&S relevance on the

building surveyor's drawings kept in the HSF. The sketchiness of the information for the HSF underlines one of the regulatory deficiencies in respect of H&S risk management on projects. For instance, the lack of policing arrangements by the Regulations to secure the quality of the File. This is an issue very pertinent to the on-going building safety reforms.

Coordination:

The Project Architect developed a good relationship with the builder. There was coordination between the Project Architect and the builder regarding temporary works on an existing beam in an external wall that was going to be affected by the extension work and thus required augmentation. Though the builder engaged the services of a Structural Engineer to do the structural analysis, calculation and advice on the management of the of the beam, the Project Architect took a keen interest in that part of the work and suggested an approach to its propping during construction. Exhibit 9 indicates the location of the existing beam in, formally, an external wall that required augmentation and delicate handling.

Meetings among dutyholders, particularly at the pre-construction stage were ad hoc and limited. Three meetings were convened and they related to:

- First, a meeting between the Client, local building surveyor and the local building control officers to sort out building control issues. Specifically, the local building control officers wanted to know how: (1) drainage from the building; and (2) electrical installation of the building were going to be addressed.
- Second, a meeting with the Client, the Project Architect and the local builder to agree on the JCT Minor Building Work Contract.
- Third, a meeting with the Client, Project Architect and the local builder to discuss and agree on the approach to manage the existing beam in, formerly, an external wall.

Apart from these main meetings, most of the communication among the dutyholders happened on the telephone and often coordinated by the Client. Further, H&S risks, particularly those that relate to the site conditions were indicated on the drawings. The Project Architect had regular telephone conversations with the local builder to draw specific attention to such risks indicated on the drawings prior to start on site.

The main challenge regarding coordination was related to the handling of a common sewer line that run at the rear garden of the building, where the extension work was required to go over. An initial assessment of it indicated a weak sewer infrastructure that required the advice of the local sewer authority before any further work could be carried out. The difficulty in having a site inspection by the local sewer authority and subsequent advice delayed pre-construction planning schedule by two months. Following the advice, the Project Architect proposed a concrete covering around the portion of the sewer line that went under the slab of the building's extension work.

Conclusions and lessons:

This case highlights an important phenomenon in the UK construction industry that domestic Clients are often not aware of CDM (i.e. H&S) issues and thus require significant support from

professionals engaged by them. Further, domestic Clients may not have extensive information about qualified builders, particularly from a H&S perspective, and as a result resort to local builders – some of whom – may be operating informally and often referred to as ‘cowboy builders’. Such engagements if unchecked could undermine H&S performance on small domestic projects. The Eden Avenue project – though a minor domestic extension work – was considered challenging, given the site restrictions (i.e. Client occupation of residence while work was to be undertaken, children playing around, and access only through the rear garden). Generally, a number of useful lessons can be gleaned from this case as follows:

- A damage to the common sewer that was later identified was not only an issue of H&S risk but also public health, considering the potential contamination to the soil and adjoining properties. Hence, issues of H&S must not necessarily be isolated and dealt with on projects but rather be considered integratively with every aspect of the project.
- Sometimes, some projects that fit the Regulations’ description for a domestic work can be very complex in its H&S attributes and management. Clients as per the current provisions in the Regulations can hide behind the relatively gentle demands on them and not take appropriate steps to formally appoint a PD for the coordination of H&S activities and processes, particularly at the pre-construction stage of the project development process. Though the Regulations indicate an automatic imposition of H&S duties on the professionals engaged by the Client, such a potential non-recognition of PD services as well as a disallowance of PD fees in the general professional fees by domestic Clients could possibly undermine the H&S outcomes on domestic projects, especially on complex ones.
- It appears more project responsibilities, which have H&S implications, are planned to be managed by builders on small or minor domestic works, right from the pre-construction stage. This, thus, highlights the need for attention to paid to the building of H&S capabilities among smaller-scale builders.
- It seems for small domestic projects, H&S capability of project participants (particularly Designers) is considered part of their general competence package by Clients. Hence, the respective professional bodies must sustain and emphasise their H&S knowledge in continuous professional development (CPD) programmes as well as accreditation of academic programmes.

EXHIBITS

Exhibit 6: Organisational structure for the delivery of health and safety

Exhibit 7: Simple project responsibility matrix

Project participant	Organisation	Role
Client	Mr James Wood	Project funding
Project Architect	Archetype Ltd	Architectural designs services
Principal Designer	Archetype	Design H&S risk management
Principal Contractor	Fawcon Ltd	Construction H&S risk management
Main Contractor	Fawcon Ltd	Construction services
Structural Engineer	ABP Consult	Structural design services
Building surveyor	Lexis Ltd	Legal and planning requirement services

Exhibit 8a: Elevations of Eden Avenue residential extension works

Exhibit 8b: Location of new sewer arrangement marked on drawings of extension area

Exhibit 8c: Excerpts of notes of H&S relevance on drawings

4. Cece Water Authority to be contacted and Build-Over Agreement to be in place before commencement of work.

5. Surface water disposal is to be taken to soakaway as a priority choice only where the substrata is suitable.

6. Agreement has been reached between neighbours for the removal of trees.

Provide mains powered, battery back-up, interlinked smoke alarms within circulation space of ground and first floors.

CWA Specifications for approved build over agreements

Sewers up to 160mm in diameter

These are our general guidelines when building within three metres or over a public sewer that is up to 160mm in diameter.

1. All new works must be done in like for like materials and comply with the requirements of the latest version of 'Sewers for Adoption', in conjunction with 'Protocol on Design and Construction of Adoption of Sewers in England and Wales'.
2. This consent is subject to any conditions that may be imposed through the Building Regulation process.
3. New dwellings are not permitted to be constructed over the public sewer.
4. Your proposed works must not transmit any additional loads to the sewer.
5. It is your responsibility to check and verify the invert levels and position of the public sewer prior to works on site.
6. Any sewers that are up to 1.1 metres deep, from ground level to invert, must run a minimum of 150 mm away from the foundations.
7. Any sewers where the invert level is more than 1.1 metres below ground level must run at least 500 mm away from the foundations. If the invert level is more than 2.0 metres below finished ground level, any proposed foundations must be at least 1.0 metre from the sewer.
8. All surveys carried out will be at the householder's expense.
9. Any piled foundations are subject to our approval and will require additional surveys to be carried out. They must be constructed a minimum of twice the pile diameter or 1.5 metres (whichever is greater) from the outside of the pile to the outside of the sewer.
10. We will not allow driven piles within 15 metres of a public sewer.
11. Manholes on the public sewer must not be built over or located inside proposed structures, even with new double-sealed bolt down covers.
12. Where the public sewer is up to 1.1 metres deep, no structure must be built in contact with the public sewer manhole, and must be a minimum of 150 mm from the outside of the chamber wall.
13. Where the public sewer is more than 1.1 metres deep, no structure must be built within 500 mm of the public manhole.

14. New connections on our existing sewer network must be constructed in like for like materials and should be via a manhole or a pre-formed junction. Saddle connections are not permitted on these sewers.

15. Connections into manholes must be made with soffit to soffit and must enter 'with the flow'.

16. We will not accept the public sewer being continuously built over for four or more properties in a row, without a suitable external manhole being available for operational access.

17. New manholes on our existing sewer network must be constructed in like for like materials and in line with the requirements of the latest version of 'Sewers for Adoption'.

18. Please note that sewers of this type are occasionally found to have minor defects such as misaligned joints (often since new) or hairline cracking. In such cases, we would accept the sewer as being in a serviceable condition.

19. We will only allow new plastic pipes and manholes where the existing sewers are constructed in plastic. All new plastic pipes constructed must be British Standards kite marked to BS EN 13476.

Foundations

Where high shrinkable clay is present, the foundations are to be no less than 1.0m below ground level and is to be at all times in accordance with NHBC standards chapter 4.2. Any species of trees identified are therefore to be confirmed by arboriculturalist and foundation design to be checked with local authority Building Control Surveyor prior to commencement of works. Where foundations are in close proximity to hedgerows or trees, protection of such foundations shall be provided in accordance with NHBC 'Building Near Trees' supplement.

Trial holes are to be dug alongside existing foundations to expose depths and condition. The contractor is to confirm the adequacy of existing foundations to take new loads and abutment of new foundations with the Building Inspector. Use C25 sulphate resisting concrete mix in foundations taken down min 1.0m deep to suitable subsoil level, recommendations of NHBC standards chapter 4.2 or to invert level of drains if deeper, to a suitable load bearing strata all to Building Inspector approval. There are no significant trees within 30m.

The subsoil at founding level shall be:

- a. Subsoil type IV or better
- b. No made up ground within load area
- c. No weaker subsoil below bearing soil
- d. Below any adjacent drainage
- e. Free and 600mm from any root or desiccation
- f. To the satisfaction of the local Building Control Officer.

It is therefore strongly recommended that a soil test is carried out to ascertain the above.

If after excavation of the foundations, the subsoil conditions etc are found to be different from those stated above; the foundations must be redesigned and submitted to the local authority for approval.

All drains runs on site should be located and identified prior to the excavating or concreting foundations. Drain runs shown on plan are assumed only. Drains passing under building are to be encased in 150mm of concrete and joints kept flexible. Drains passing through excavation to be isolated from the foundation to CP111.

General

Do not scale from this drawing.

The contractor is to visit the site prior to commencement of the works and before tendering/quoting and determine the location and suitability of any existing foundations, other load bearing elements of structure, services, drains (including inverts) and trees.

The contractor will also ascertain all boundaries, levels, dimensions and information on site prior to commencement of work. Any discrepancies are to be reported to the designer immediately and no responsibility will be taken for the building works on site as no site supervision will take place during construction. The plans are provided for the purpose of applying for building regulation and town planning consent only. Prior to commencing works the contractor should be provided with a copy of the latest revision of all plans and calculations. Compliance with the requirements of any other statutory bodies is the responsibility of the contractor. All work to be carried out in accordance with the current building regulations, public health regulations, British standards, codes of practice and the technical regulations of the NHBC.

The local authority building inspector shall be invited to inspect any work prior to covering up. The contractor should be aware of his obligations under the Construction (Design and Management) Regulations. The designer has not undertaken the role of planning supervisor nor Party-Wall Surveyor / Advisor

The property owner should establish any local restrictions, boundary problems, easements, covenants etc and obtain, before commencement of work, any written consent from the relevant party for access onto neighbouring land. There is to be no encroachment of any work over any boundary. Where required the adjacent land owners' permission to render is to be obtained in writing prior to commencement of work.

Party wall act 1996

Under the party wall act 1996 etc. The building owner is required to give written notices (in a specified format) to adjoining owners, if the works fall within the scope of the act.

To find out if the party wall act applies you are advised to seek advice from a surveyor who specialises in this field.

Building over or near to a public sewer.

An agreement may need to be entered into with the local water authority. Prior to the commencement of any work, you should contact the relevant Water Authority to determine the proximity of their assets.

Demolition, Alterations and Stripping Out

The contractor, when instructed to demolish any buildings or part of buildings shall ensure safety of the remaining part of the building by the provision of shores or other temporary supports and shall leave and protect any supporting buttresses, angles etc or existing brick work.

The contractor is to notify adjoining owners before commencing site operations. The contractor is to make good any holes left by stripping out, taking up the floor slabs, grubbing up foundations or other works.

The contractor is to remove all rubbish and debris from the site to the satisfaction of the client without annoyance to the adjoining property owners. The contractor will be responsible for ascertaining and accounting for the extent of all rubbish and debris prior to tender.

Any excavations near the foundations of existing walls or adjoining buildings shall be carefully carried out and where necessary the existing foundations shall be underpinned and made secure after the written permission of the adjoining owner. The contractor is responsible and liable for any damage to existing services and must arrange for disconnecting or protection of services as required by the building work.

Where excavation, demolition or other building work is likely to expose gas, water, electrical or other existing services, the contractor shall immediately notify the respective authority to arrange necessary protection of the service.

Exhibit 9: Augmented existing beam in, formally, an external wall

